

First-Year Students' Perspectives on Library Use: A Survey-Based Study

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Abstract: *This study examines the perspectives, habits, and expectations of first-year students regarding library usage at Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya, an undergraduate college under the West Bengal State University for the academic years 2023-2024 and 2024-2025. The transition from school to college presents students with new academic challenges, and the library often becomes a pivotal support resource. This study gathers information about students' past experiences with school and public libraries, present library use patterns, and future expectations by surveying them during the initial library registration process. A survey based study was carried out with a structured questionnaire consisting of 15 questions to 270 students across both academic years. Analysis of the data shows that people strongly value library resources, prefer print and digital versions, and have high expectations for study spaces, computer and internet access, and support systems. The study offers actionable recommendations to improve library services and user engagement. The results emphasize how academic libraries must change to meet students' changing information needs.*

Keywords: Library Use, Undergraduate Students

1 Introduction

An essential component of higher education is the academic library, which gives students access to resources, guidance, and a supportive learning environment. This facility frequently marks a substantial change for first-year students compared to their prior experiences in public libraries or schools. Developing responsive and efficient library services requires an understanding of how new college students perceive and expect to use the library. Many of the students at Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya, a college affiliated with West Bengal State University, come from a variety of socioeconomic and educational backgrounds. The purpose of this study was to investigate first-year students' expectations and experiences with libraries as they begin their college careers. By conducting the survey during the mandatory library card registration process, the study ensures inclusivity and relevance. The research captures students' library usage habits formed during their school days, their exposure to public libraries, and their aspirations from the college library. These

insights help college librarians as well as administrators align services with student needs, promoting greater utilization and academic success.

2 Review of Literature

The results of a seven-year longitudinal survey that was carried out between 2016 and 2022 and looked at first-year undergraduate students in the information management program's adoption of e-books are presented in the study by Nahotko & Deja (2004). According to the survey, students have long considered e-books to be an essential tool for acquiring exploratory knowledge, especially in the social sciences. Bloom, Eller, Hall, Lang, and Sample's study from 2025 looks into the connection between students' academic achievement and how often they use the library. The results show that more library visits lead to better academic performance, underscoring the library's critical function as a place where students can succeed. The purpose of the study conducted by Adetayo, Asiru, and Oladokun (2024) is to look into the factors that affect university students' decision not to enroll in LIS programs. 537 students were given a survey to gauge their views on librarians, the value of university libraries, and the reasons they did not pursue library and information science studies. The findings show that people have very favorable views of librarians as informed, personable experts who get along well with others.

Liu's (2025) current scientific article's primary goal is to empirically examine how students' utilization of library resources affects their information literacy abilities. The study focuses on the processes of choosing and processing information as well as critical thinking abilities. The article by Hodge (2022) explains the usefulness of academic capital and library anxiety as theoretical frameworks to inform future research on first-generation students and first-year students, respectively, and critiques the current state of the literature on first-year first-generation students. It also identifies important areas for additional study. In their study, Bodhinayaka, Jamali, Hider, and Carroll (2025) investigated how pre-admission students in Sri Lanka acquire their prior knowledge about academic libraries based on their contacts with different information sources and personal library experiences. Through an interpretive perspective and Charmaz's constructivist grounded theory methodology, the study took a qualitative approach.

3 Scope and Coverage of the Study

This study focuses exclusively on first-year undergraduate students of Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya during the academic years 2023-2024 and 2024-2025. It includes students from all streams, such as science, arts and commerce and departments who visited the college library to register for a library card. The scope is limited to their past experiences with libraries (school or public libraries), current usage habits, preferred resource formats, and expectations from the college library. The findings are based on the survey conducted during the months of August to December in each academic year. The study is limited to students of one college library only.

4 Objectives of the Study

- To assess first-year students' prior experience with school and public libraries.
- To analyze current library usage habits and preferences.
- To identify students' expectations from the college library.
- To offer actionable recommendations to improve academic library services.

5 Methodology

5.1 Research Design: A quantitative, descriptive research design was used for this study and data was collected through a structured questionnaire administered in person during library card registration of first year students.

5.2 Population and Sample: The population consisted of all first-year students who came to the library for new library card registration during the academic years 2023-2024 and 2024-2025. A total of 270 students participated (140 from 2023-2024 and 130 from 2024-2025) and the students were selected via convenience sampling.

5.3 Data Collection Tool: A structured questionnaire with 15 questions was developed. The questionnaire was divided into four sections: demographic information, past library experience, current usage habits, and future expectations.

5.4 Data Analysis: Data was analyzed and interpreted using basic statistical techniques and represented using tables and charts.

6 Data Analysis and Interpretation

6.1 Demographic Information

Figure 1: Demographic Information of Students

From figure 1 it is shown that a total of 134 male and 136 female students have been selected for this study during two academic sessions. Most of these students came from Arts stream. From the college admission data it is found that most of the students take their admission into Arts and Humanities stream and a very few students take admission in the other two streams.

6.2 Past library use behaviour of students

Figure 2: Past Library Use Behaviour of Students

Figure 3: Frequency of Library Use

Total number of users who have past experience with school and/or public library use is 158, that is 58% and most of them are users of the school library. Total 18 of the 270 students have experience with public libraries that is 7 percent of total population. From the figure 2 it is also found that students of science stream have more familiarities with libraries. During the verbal communication most of them respond that they do not have any knowledge about public libraries. They used the school library sometimes only for their academic needs.

Figure 3 shows that frequency of library use is also not on a regular basis. Students used the school as well as the public libraries occasionally.

6.3 Current usage habits

Table 1: Current usage habits (N=158)

Main purpose of library visits	No. of students
Reading textbooks or reference books	158
Borrowing books	137
Internet access	3
Reading newspapers, magazines, etc.	11

The table 1 shows that almost all students with prior library experience reported using it for reading textbooks and reference books. This demonstrates a strong academic orientation in their library usage habits, with a focus on syllabus-oriented materials and supplementary academic content. Only a small number of students had used internet services within their past library experiences. Similarly, reading newspapers or magazines was also not a common activity among them. This suggests a potential gap in exposure to broader learning materials and a dependence on print books over other formats.

6.4. Expectations from the College Library

Table 2: Expectations from the college library (N=270)

Facilities / Services	Yes	No	May be
Textbooks	262	6	2
Reference books	193	48	29
Journals and magazines	236	5	29
Digital resources (e-books, e-journals, online databases)	177	53	40
Career Counselling Books/Magazines	242	15	13
Computers for study/academic use	249	5	16
Internet access	214	42	14
Wi-Fi Facility	252	0	18
Orientation sessions or user training workshops	155	27	88
Group study rooms/space	171	27	72
Quiet reading areas	164	63	43
Printing and photocopying services	246	12	12
Assistance from library staff (help finding resources, research help)	188	34	48

From the above table it is revealed that the students have high demand for core academic resources. The vast majority of students expressed an obvious need for textbooks as well as reference books. They also clearly indicate that they need print journals and magazines. Students in addition mentioned their expectations about digital resources. Approximately 66% of students stated that they expected access to digital academic contents such as e-books, online journals, and databases. This highlights a growing shift toward hybrid learning preferences that combine print and digital formats. Students of today's generation are also more aware about their career. The study revealed that about 90 percent of students expect availability and access to the resources related directly to their career development. Technological infrastructure is a basic need for today's education. Majority of students anticipated the availability of computers and reliable internet or Wi-Fi services in the library.

Students also demand for purposeful study spaces. A lot of respondents emphasized the importance of group discussion rooms and quiet study areas. Students expressed a desire for flexible environments that support both collaborative and individual learning styles. A moderate number of students selected "Maybe" when asked about library orientation or training sessions, reflecting unfamiliarity with such offerings. This suggests an opportunity to meet the students and share the information about the services or facilities that a college can provide. Unfamiliarity leading to uncertainty, that's why around 20–25% of students chose "Maybe" for services like access to databases or digital tools, indicating they may not have used such resources previously. This group requires targeted awareness and training to fully engage with library services.

In spite of varying levels of awareness, the overall response indicates that first-year students recognize the library as a vital academic resource. There is a clear willingness among the majority to explore and use multiple services provided by the library.

7 Findings and Conclusion

This survey-based study examines first-year students' perceptions and finds both consistency and change in their expectations and behaviors toward library use. According to the results, the majority of students who previously used school or public libraries did so mainly to study reference materials and textbooks. A significant 90% also utilized borrowing facilities, reflecting a strong academic motivation behind library visits.

However, there was a notably low level of participation with non-academic reading materials and digital tools. Just a small percentage of students said they read newspapers, used the internet, or read general interest periodicals. This suggests a narrow focus in prior library use, likely shaped by limited infrastructure and digital access in earlier library settings.

The results of the study reveal that although school libraries are commonly available, students' usage of these facilities varies significantly, often depending on the resources and assistance offered. Many students had access to school libraries, but the inconsistency in how frequently and effectively they were used indicates a lack of structured engagement or participation. However, just a small percentage of students had previously used public libraries, indicating that they were either underutilized or had accessibility or outreach problems.

However, students expressed a noticeable excitement for using academic libraries after they started college. When they are informed about the availability of contemporary amenities like internet connectivity, digital access points, and well-organized study spaces, their optimistic attitude becomes even more obvious. There is a significant desire to investigate services that extend beyond

conventional books, indicating a readiness to move toward more dynamic and technologically assisted teaching methods.

Students' expectations from the college library are clearly high. They prioritize improved infrastructure, access to up-to-date study aids, and organized spaces helpful to focused learning. Additionally, their willingness to participate in library orientation programs highlights a proactive approach toward gaining familiarity with the library environment. This willingness shows that students not only appreciate the library as a resource but are also eager to enhance their understanding of how to navigate and utilize it effectively for academic growth.

In general, the study shows that students are going through a transitional stage during which they keep their current habits while remaining open to adopting new services and resources. Libraries need to help with this change by providing a variety of services, enhancing accessibility, and raising awareness through training sessions and orientations. By doing this, college libraries can develop into welcoming environments that accommodate a greater range of learning styles and academic requirements.

8 Recommendations

- Conduct regular orientation sessions and library tours for new students.
- Increase digital content offerings, including e-books and academic databases. Introduce training programs to familiarize students with digital resources, including e-books, academic databases, and online journals.
- Ensure reliable internet access and adequate computer terminals within the library to support digital learning.
- Encourage students to engage with newspapers, magazines, and general knowledge resources in addition to textbooks.
- Create more individual and group study spaces.
- Establish a feedback mechanism to continually assess student needs and improve services accordingly.
- Collaborate with faculty to integrate library use into curriculum assignments.

These steps will not only align the library's offerings with student expectations but also empower learners by bridging the gap between traditional and modern information access.

Bibliographical References:

Adetayo, Adebawale Jeremy, Asiru, Mufutau Ayobami & Oladokun, Bolaji David. (2024). Student perceptions of libraries and librarians: Factors in non-enrollment in LIS programs. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102935>.

Bloom, Myra, Eller, Daniel, Mark, Hall, Andrew & Sample, Angela. (2025). The impact of library visits on undergraduate student GPA: The vital role of the library as a contributor to student success. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 51(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2025.103040>.

- Bodhinayaka, Dilini, Jamali, Hamid R., Hider, Philip & Carroll, Mary. (2025). Pre-admission undergraduate students' prior understanding of academic libraries in Sri Lanka. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 51(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2025.103029>.
- Hodge, Megan L. (2022). First-generation students and the first-year transition: State of the literature and implications for library researchers. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 48(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2022.102554>.
- Liu, Man. (2025). Information Literacy Formation through the Use of Library Resources: Thinking, Selection, and Information Processing Skills of Students. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2025.101789>.
- Nahotko, Marek & Deja, Marek. (2024). E-book acceptance by first-year undergraduate students: A longitudinal examination and implications for library researchers. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102847>.